

Synthetic Humic Acids as Polyelectrolytes : Viscosity Studies

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Synthetic humic acids have been prepared from each of glucose, catechol and hydroquinone with or without amino acids as the source of nitrogen. The humus formed was separated with sodium hydroxide solution by centrifugation from which humic acids were precipitated with hydrochloric acid at pH 2-3. They were purified by repeating the process of dissolution and precipitation and finally by dialysis and electro dialysis. The sodium salts of these humic acids have been subjected to viscometric studies which reveal their polyelectrolytic nature.

IN recent years several investigators¹⁻³ have demonstrated polyelectrolytic behaviour of coal humic and peat humic acids from viscosity measurements. These observations are not in agreement with those made by Flaig and Bœutelspacher⁴, who, from viscosity studies of both natural and synthetic humic acids suggested particularly for the latter, a spherical shape rather the polyelectrolytic chain. In the face of these divergent views we have considered it worthwhile to investigate the polyelectrolytic character of synthetic humic acids. In this paper the results of viscosity measurements carried out with humic acids and their sodium salts have been reported and their polyelectrolytic behaviour discussed in the light of these measurements.

Viscosity study at once reveals the polyelectrolytic character of the dissolved species. Unlike neutral polymers polyelectrolytes show sharp rise in viscosity i.e., η_{sp}/c with decreasing concentration. Fuoss⁵ has attributed this to increased coulombic repulsion amongst similarly charged centres on the polymer molecule leading to its extension

At infinite dilution ionisation is virtually complete and the polymer molecule assumes the maximum possible extension. In addition, there are electroviscous effects caused by counter ion atmosphere of the macro ions and the long range electrostatic intermolecular coupling. The upward rise of η_{sp}/C with decreasing concentration is explained in this way. In the more concentrated region the counter ions become bound to the polymer molecule thereby neutralising some of the charged sites. As a consequence the polymer coils up and when the concentration is large enough the polymer behaves more or less like a neutral polymer. The same effect is also brought about by addition of neutral salt when a linear graph of η_{sp}/c vs C is observed, making extrapolation possible. Fuoss and Cathers⁶ have proposed the following equations for polyelectrolytes.

$$Z = \eta_{sp}/c = \frac{A}{1+B\sqrt{C}} + D \quad \dots (1)$$

where A , B and D are constants. According to this equation a plot of C/η_{sp} vs C will be linear when D is small. By extrapolation, the intrinsic viscosity of salt-free polyelectrolyte may then be determined. A and B measure respectively the extension of the polyelectrolyte and electrostatic forces. The intrinsic viscosity is related⁷ to the volumes of the components of a binary solution of rigid macromolecules as follows.

$$[\eta] = \nu \frac{N}{M} V_n = \nu(\bar{v}_2 + \delta_1 v_1^0) \quad \dots (2)$$

- where V_n = hydrodynamic volume of the macromolecule
- \bar{v}_2 = partial sp. vol. (c.c./gm) of solute.
- v_1^0 = Sp. vol. of solvent.
- δ_1 = solvation expressed in gms. of solvent associated with one gm. of solute, and
- ν = Simha's shape factor.

ν and δ_1 , cannot therefore, be evaluated from measurement of viscosity alone. But the maximum values of δ_1 for $\nu = 2.5$ i.e., the maximum value for spherical particles can be easily calculated. The radius⁸ of this assumed sphere is then obtained by setting $V_n = 4/3\pi R^3$. Alternatively, the maximum value of ν corresponding to maximum asymmetry can be obtained by setting $\delta_1 = 0$. The observed value of ν can then be interpreted in terms of the ellipsoidal model of Simha. Knowing the axial ratio (a/b) of ellipsoids of revolution from Simha's^{9a} graph of ν vs a/b the ratios of the frictional coefficient (f/f_0) corresponding to those ellipsoids can be evaluated from Perrin's f/f_0 vs a/b graphs^{9b}. Without regard to the electrostatic effects the intrinsic viscosities of polyelectrolytes measured at reasonably high ionic strength may be then utilised to get an idea of their

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sizes and shapes. $[\eta]$ of the salt-free polyelectrolyte obtained from Fuoss-Cathers plot can be utilised, as was shown by Oth and Doty⁹, to calculate the effective root-mean square separation, $(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, between the ends of the polymer molecule by means of the well known Flory-Fox equation viz.,

$$(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\bar{M}[\eta]}{\phi} \quad \dots (3)$$

where ϕ is an universal constant, independent of solute-solvent systems and has an experimental average value of 21×10^{21} . If M is the number average molecular weight, $(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ has also the number average value, and if \bar{M} is the weight average molecular weight the radius will have a 'Z' average value.

Materials and Methods

The methods of preparing the synthetic humic acids have been described in detail elsewhere¹⁰

The sodium salts of the respective humic acids were prepared by neutralising the acids with NaOH and then precipitating and washing with 95% neutral alcohol. The salts were dried in vacuum at 85°.

and the standard deviation was less than 0.08 sec. This would result in an error of < 1.7% in the computed values of η_{sp}/c over the concentration range studied

Results and Discussion

The viscosity measurement represented in Figs. 1-4 show typical features of polyelectrolytes** The evaluated constants of Fuoss-Cathers equation (1) are given in Table 1, which shows that HQ-H possesses greater *A* and *B* values indicating a greater flexibility as well as stronger electrostatic interaction

Fuoss and Strauss¹¹ have shown that a linear graph is obtained by plotting $[\eta]^{-3}$ vs μ^{-1} especially at high ionic strength (μ). From such a Fuoss plot constructed from the measured value of $[\eta]_{0.1MNaCl}$ and $[\eta]_0$ obtained from Fuoss Cathers plot, $[\eta]_{0.25MNaCl}$ was evaluated. Table 2 gives $[\eta]_0$ values at these different ionic strengths. The values of $[\eta]_{0.25MNaCl}$ have been used elsewhere¹⁰. The low $[\eta]$ values and their variation with ionic strength show very weak polyelectrolytic character of these synthetic preparations compared to other synthetic polyelectrolytes.

Fig. 1. ○ -- Na-hydroquinone humate (salt free)
 ● -- Na-hydroquinone humate (reciprocal plot)
 ● -- Na-hydroquinone humate (in 0.125 M NaCl)
 ⊗ -- Na-hydroquinone humate (in 0.01 M NaCl)

The viscosity measurements of solutions of these salts were carried out in a Cannon-Fenske viscometer having a flow time of 226.95 secs. for 5.0 ml of distilled water at 35°. All measurements were done in a thermostat maintained at 35° ± 0.01° by a toluene vapour thermoregulator operating in conjunction with an electronic relay system. The solutions being dilute their densities were taken to be the same as that of water. The values of partial specific volumes measured according to method reported elsewhere¹⁰ are simply quoted here for the purpose of calculation.

Flow times of viscosity measurement were reproducible within ± 0.1 sec. so that the mean deviation in observed flow times was less than 0.07 sec.,

This is not unexpected in view of their low molecular weights and probably also from the stiffness of the molecules owing to the presence of aromatic chains. Branching is also known to decrease the

** The kink in η_{sp}/C Plot (Fig. 1) for HQ-Na in 0.01 N NaCl may arise out of a higher observed value of η_{sp}/C in higher concentration region than would be expected from extrapolation from dilute region. This was found reproducible. As the results in the dilute region become more and more uncertain because of systematic error of dilution being many times multiplied in the computed values of η_{sp}/C , and since the exponential curve could not be drawn with proper weighting on each point, the observed kink may or may not be significant.

Fig. 2 ○ — Na-Catechol humate (salt free)
 ■ — Na-Catechol humate (reciprocal plot)
 ● — Na-Catechol humate (in 0.1M NaCl)

Fig. 3 ○ — Na-Catechol humate (by O₂) (salt free)
 ■ — Na-Catechol humate (reciprocal plot)
 ● — Na-Catechol humate (in 0.1M NaCl)

Fig. 4 ○ — Na-glucose humate (salt free)
 ■ — Na-glucose humate (reciprocal plot)
 ● — Na-glucose humate (in 0.1M NaCl)

Fig. 5 ○ — Catechol humic acid (by O₂)
 △ — Catechol humic acid
 ▲ — Glucose humic acid
 ● — Hydroquinone humic acid

TABLE 1. EVALUATION OF FUOSS-CATHERS CONSTANTS

System	$D' = [\eta]_z$ dl/g.	$\frac{B}{A}$	A	B
HQ-Na	0.029	24.5	0.323	7.92
CT-Na	0.025	27.1	0.169	4.60
CA-Na	0.024	31.1	0.164	5.10
GL-Na	0.023	21.8	0.171	3.73

intrinsic viscosity. Natural humic acid salts show a lower intrinsic viscosity¹² than their synthetic counterparts presumably due to a greater flexibility and/or smaller extent of branching in the latter. Table 3 gives plausible values of the parameters connected with the size and shape of the synthetic acid salt preparations calculated from equation (2). On the basis of the approximations mentioned earlier the maximum hydration of the synthetic humic acid salts ranges from 0.8 gm. to 1.3 gm. and the radii of the corresponding spheres lie within 7.1 to 8.4° A, the rather low values being in conformity with their low molecular weight. On the other hand if we ignore solvation and compute the maximum asymmetry of the molecules, the axial ratios of prolate ellipsoids figure out as 7.9, 4.9

and 5.6 for HQ-Na, CT-Na and GL-Na respectively, whereas on the basis of an oblate model the corresponding values are 12.8, 6.7 and 7.8. It is probable that the molecules are neither highly solvated nor highly asymmetric but it is likely that both these factors are responsible to different extents for their actual hydrodynamic behaviour. Viscosity measurements alone cannot give an idea of the shape and extent of solvation but by comparing with diffusion measurement¹⁰, it is possible to suggest that the humate molecules probably agree in their behaviour with the model of weakly solvated prolate ellipsoids.

Some workers¹³ have applied Simha's equation for ellipsoidal particles to obtain reasonable values of molecular dimensions from viscosity of polyelectrolytes at zero or low ionic strength, when the polyelectrolyte molecule is fully stretched. Doty¹⁴ *et al.*, also have successfully applied this equation in the case of poly- γ -benzyl-glutamate assuming rod like configuration in chloroform-formamide solution and a rigid structure. They have, however, extended the idea to cylinders of high asymmetry rather than ellipsoids of revolution (*loc. cit.*).

The intrinsic viscosities of salt-free poly- γ -benzyl-glutamate have been discussed by Oth and Doty⁹ in the light of Flory-Fox equation (3). For this

TABLE 2. MOLECULAR WEIGHT FROM VISCOSITY AND DIFFUSION MEASUREMENTS.

System	$[\eta]_{0.1M NaCl}$ ml/g.	$[\eta]_{0.25M NaCl}$ ml/g. (Fuoss plot)	$[\eta]_{Salt free}$ c.c./g. (Fuoss-Cathers plot)	v_2		Mol' wt \bar{M} from combined diffusion and viscosity data
				In water	In 0.25M NaCl soln.	
HQ-Na	4.5	3.80	35.5	0.42	0.44	830
CT-Na	3.5	3.11	18.2	0.56	0.58	795
CA-Na	4.4	3.51	17.3	—	—	—
GL-Na	3.6	3.05	16.51	0.60	0.53	628

purpose, they employed \bar{M}_w from light scattering measurements. The calculated value of $(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is in good agreement with that obtained from dissymmetry measurement. They, however, interpreted dissymmetry on the random coil model, because at high degree of ionisation using rod models would require that the molecule would be stretched to over half its contour length. This work has been continued by Oth¹⁵, with substances of smaller molecule being believed to extend almost to a rod-like configuration upon ionisation in the absence of salt. The dimensions calculated from both viscosity and light scattering data using equations for a rod model agree well.

TABLE 3. SOLVATION/ASYMMETRY CALCULATED FROM

System	Maximum Solvation ($\nu = 2.5$)		Maximum asymmetry ($\delta_1 = 0$)		
	δ_1 g/g	Radius of Corresponding Sphere Re(Å)	Shape factor ν	a/b , prolate ellipsoids	a/b , oblate ellipsoids
HQ-Na	1.35	8.4	10.2	7.90	12.8
CT-Na	0.82	7.6	6.03	4.95	6.70
GL-Na	0.90	7.1	6.75	5.60	7.60

The agreement sought by Oth and Doty⁹ does not appear to be generally valid even in the case of

polyelectrolytes having sufficiently high molecular weights to justify application to statistical theories. Calculations¹⁶ made with a number of polymeric substances show that the average end to end distance of the polymer obtained from light scattering measurement with random coil model is much larger than that obtained from the Flory-Fox equation. On the other hand, with rod model the light scattering value is nearly twice that calculated from the Flory-Fox equation. When the molecule is fully stretched, assuming it to be a rod of high asymmetry and taking the length of the rod $L = 2X(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ where $(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is calculated from Flory-Fox equation, the diameter 'd' of the cylinder could be calculated (column 4, Table 4) from

$$M = \frac{\pi d^2 L}{4V_2} \quad \dots (4)$$

Also where the molecules exist as actual rigid rods at all concentrations, the ratio L/d was found to be equal to the axial ratios of prolate ellipsoids obtained from Simha's equation. But when the molecules were actually random coil but fully stretched, the axial ratios of the equivalent prolate ellipsoids calculated from L/d as

$$a/b = (2/3)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{L}{d} \quad \dots (5)$$

were in excellent agreement (column 6, Table 4), with those obtained from Simha's equation. In view of all these observations, similar calculations were carried out with the synthetic humic acid salts.

Fig. 6 ● — Hydroquinone humic acid
 □ — Catechol humic acid
 Δ — Catechol humic acid
 ○ — Glucose humic acid

TABLE 4

System	Solvent	$(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ from Flory-Fox Equn. (Å)	Cylinder model Diameter 'D' (Å)	Cylinder model L/d	Axial ratio of equivalent prolate ellipsoid	Axial ratio prolate ellipsoid; Simha's $(a/b)\nu$
HQ-Na	Salt free aqueous solution	51.4	2.68	38.41	31.4	30.7
CT-Na	"	41.0	3.37	24.3	19.9	17.3
GL-Na	"	36.7	3.29	22.3	18.2	15.4

The results have been shown in Table 4, which indicate a random coil nature of the humate molecules. However, this conclusion is made with due reservation because of the low molecular weights of these synthetic preparations¹⁰.

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